

The Current Status of Artificial Intelligence Application in Early Childhood Education in Vietnam

Phan Tu Anh

Faculty of Pedagogy, Thu Dau Mot University, Viet Nam

ABSTRACT: Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly seen as a potential tool to promote innovation and improve the quality of education, including early childhood education. The application of AI in early childhood education in Vietnam is still relatively new, lacking clear guidance and direction. Understanding the current state of AI application in this educational level is essential. This article focuses on analyzing the awareness, application level, benefits, and challenges of integrating AI into early childhood education in Vietnam. The study uses a questionnaire survey with a 5-point Likert scale, conducted on 150 participants, including 100 early childhood teachers and 50 administrators. The results show that the majority of participants have a basic understanding of AI, and its application is mainly limited to information searching and assisting with simple tasks. Furthermore, AI is considered to have many benefits, such as supporting and increasing children's interest in educational and play activities, and reducing the workload for teachers. However, the implementation of AI in preschool education still faces many obstacles, such as limitations in facilities, teachers lacking knowledge and technological skills, and concerns related to ethics and data security for children.

KEYWORDS: Artificial intelligence; early childhood education; current state of artificial intelligence application; digital transformation in education.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is gradually asserting its position and role in all areas of social life today; especially in early childhood education, AI is also having an impact and is gradually changing the quality of education at this level globally. In Vietnam, the application of AI in early childhood education, although still in its initial stages of exploration and application, has been spontaneous and nascent, lacking systematic guidance, but it has shown benefits in the care and education of children. AI helps support and actively enhance children's activities, learning, and play; suggests learning and activity ideas to teachers that are appropriate for children's characteristics, and optimizes teachers' professional work and classroom management. However, the application of AI in early childhood education faces many challenges such as ensuring the security of children's data and information, the digital literacy of teachers, and the requirements for necessary facilities and digital equipment in preschools. Therefore, a systematic study of the theoretical basis and current state of AI application in early childhood education in Vietnam is necessary to outline the current situation and provide a scientific basis for developing appropriate educational policies and practices in the coming period.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article uses a mixed-methods approach, combining literature review and field survey to analyze the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in early childhood education in Vietnam.

The literature review method involves collecting and analyzing domestic and international research related to AI in education, thereby building the theoretical basis and analytical framework for the article.

The field survey was conducted with 150 participants, including 100 teachers and 50 administrators at preschools in urban and suburban areas of Ho Chi Minh City, encompassing both public and private schools. Data was collected through questionnaires using a 5-point Likert scale, focusing on: awareness of AI, level of application, benefits, and difficulties.

The data was processed using descriptive statistics methods including frequency, percentage, and mean values.

RESULT

3.1. Theoretical basis

Artificial intelligence (AI) is understood as the ability of computer systems to perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, reasoning, recognition, and decision-making (OECD, 2019; UNESCO, 2021).

The Current Status of Artificial Intelligence Application in Early Childhood Education in Vietnam

In the field of education, AI is considered a powerful tool to support innovation in teaching methods and educational management (Holmes et al., 2019).

In early childhood education, the application of AI needs to be approached based on the developmental characteristics of young children. According to modern educational perspectives, preschool children learn through experience, interaction, and exploration of their surrounding environment. Therefore, AI should not replace the role of teachers but should act as a supporting tool to improve the quality of educational activities.

Several foundational theories can be used to explain the role of AI in early childhood education, including: (1) Constructivism theory emphasizes the active role of learners in constructing knowledge through experience (Jean Piaget, 1970; Lev Vygotsky, 1978). In the current context, AI can support the design of personalized learning environments, tailored to the needs and abilities of each child (Holmes et al., 2019). (2) Social Learning Theory emphasizes the role of social interaction in the learning process (Albert Bandura, 1977). Accordingly, the application of AI in early childhood education should aim to support interaction between children and teachers and peers, rather than replacing these existing social relationships in the educational environment. (3) The Digital Pedagogy approach emphasizes the meaningful and appropriate integration of technology into teaching in accordance with educational goals (UNESCO, 2021). In this approach, AI is considered a component of the educational technology ecosystem, contributing to improving the efficiency and flexibility of the teaching process (Holmes et al., 2019).

Thus, from the above theories, it can be seen that the application of AI in preschool education needs to ensure the principle of child-centered learning, while maintaining the leading role of teachers in organizing and directing educational activities.

3.2. Current status of awareness and application of AI in preschool education

A survey of 150 participants (100 teachers and 50 administrators) revealed that current awareness of AI in early childhood education is at an average level. Specifically, the average level of understanding of AI reached a mean of 3.42, indicating that the majority of participants had some initial understanding of AI, but not a deep or systematic one.

Approximately 68% of those surveyed stated they had heard of or had basic knowledge of AI, while only 24% believed they understood how AI operates and its applications in early childhood education. This reflects the gap between awareness, information, and the ability to apply them in practice.

Regarding application, AI is currently mainly used as a tool for querying information and supporting teachers' work. Specifically, 72% of teachers reported using AI in lesson planning (Mean = 3.95), 69% used AI for information searching (Mean = 3.88), and 74% used AI to generate ideas for educational activities (Mean = 4.02). However, the direct application of AI in children's learning activities remains limited, with an average value of only 2.76, indicating that AI has not yet been deeply integrated into the learning environment of preschool children. Notably, there are differences between regions. Teachers in urban areas have a higher level of awareness and use of AI (Mean = 3.68) compared to those in suburban areas (Mean = 3.21). This result suggests a certain gap in skills regarding the approach and application of technology in preschool education between different groups of teachers in these areas.

3.3. The benefits of AI for early childhood education.

The survey results show that participants highly appreciate the benefits that AI brings to early childhood education, especially in three main aspects. Firstly, AI supports the suggestion of learning and play activities for children, with an average rating of 3.85 (Mean). AI technology can suggest content and activities suitable to each child's abilities and needs, contributing to improved educational effectiveness. Secondly, AI contributes to increased interest and participation in learning activities (Mean = 3.92). Highly interactive AI tools help create a more vibrant and engaging learning environment for young children. Thirdly, the most highly rated benefit is the ability to reduce the workload for teachers (Mean = 4.21). The majority of teachers stated that AI helps them save time in lesson planning, designing learning materials, and finding ideas for organizing activities, thus allowing them more time to focus on caring for and interacting with children. Overall, the results suggest that AI is currently perceived primarily as a tool to assist teachers rather than a tool that directly impacts children's learning.

3.4. Difficulties and challenges in integrating AI into early childhood education

Besides its benefits, the integration of AI into early childhood education also faces many difficulties and challenges.

First, the lack of AI training is considered the biggest barrier, with an average Mean rating of 4.26. The majority of teachers reported not having participated in formal training courses on AI in education. Next is the limited digital literacy of teachers (Mean = 4.18). Many teachers still struggle with using technological tools, especially complex AI tools. Furthermore, infrastructure and technology are also significant obstacles (Mean = 4.05), particularly in educational institutions in suburban areas where equipment is limited. In addition, concerns about ethics and data security are also noted at a relatively high level (Mean = 3.89). Approximately 61% of survey participants expressed concerns about the security of personal information and the potential negative impacts of AI on young children.

The Current Status of Artificial Intelligence Application in Early Childhood Education in Vietnam

4. DISCUSSION

Research results show that the application of artificial intelligence in early childhood education in Vietnam is in its initial stages, characterized by a moderate level of awareness and application. This aligns with the general trend in developing countries, where AI in education is still in the testing and development phase.

Firstly, the survey results indicate that although most teachers and administrators have a preliminary understanding of AI, their knowledge is limited and not systematic. This highlights the urgent need for training and capacity building in technology for early childhood educators. The lack of a foundational knowledge of AI may be the reason why its application in practice has not been truly effective.

Secondly, AI is currently primarily used as a tool to support teachers' work, rather than being directly integrated into children's learning activities. This result reflects the reality that early childhood education still focuses on direct interaction between teachers and children, while the application of technology needs careful consideration to ensure it is appropriate for the developmental characteristics of young children. Furthermore, a noteworthy finding is the difference between urban and suburban areas in the level of access to and use of AI, indicating the existence of a certain digital divide. This necessitates the implementation of supportive policies from the State and relevant stakeholders to ensure equitable access to technology across regions.

In terms of benefits, AI is highly valued for its ability to reduce the workload for teachers, demonstrating its great potential in improving the efficiency of educational management and organization. However, if it only plays a supporting role, AI will not be able to fully realize its potential in innovating teaching methods. Finally, barriers related to infrastructure, digital capabilities, and especially the lack of specialized AI training further highlight the need for AI technology integration to follow a clear roadmap with synchronized investment from policy to practice. Ultimately, issues related to ethics and data security also require special attention, especially in the context of early childhood education.

From the above results, it can be affirmed that the application of AI in early childhood education in Vietnam has great potential, but effective implementation requires a combination of enhancing teacher capacity, improving infrastructure, and developing a suitable policy framework.

5. CONCLUSION

This study analyzed the current state of awareness and application of artificial intelligence in early childhood education in Vietnam through a combination of theoretical overview and practical survey methods. The results show that AI is gradually being accessed and used in early childhood education institutions; however, the level of application remains limited and mainly focuses on supporting teachers' work. AI offers many significant benefits such as actively supporting learning activities, increasing children's interest, and especially reducing the workload for teachers. However, the integration process still faces many difficulties related to teachers' digital skills, infrastructure conditions, and ethical and data security issues. Therefore, it can be affirmed that the application of AI in early childhood education in Vietnam has potential for development, but needs to be implemented according to a suitable roadmap. Focusing on enhancing teachers' capabilities, increasing investment in technological infrastructure, and developing guidelines for the safe and effective use of AI are key factors.

REFERENCES

- 1) Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Prentice Hall.
- 2) Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial intelligence in education: Promises and implications for teaching and learning*. Center for Curriculum Redesign. <https://curriculumredesign.org/wp-content/uploads/AIED-Report-2019.pdf>
- 3) OECD (2019). *Artificial intelligence in society*. Paris: OECD Publishing. https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/artificial-intelligence-in-society_eedfee77-en.html
- 4) Jiahong Su a và Weipeng Yang (2023), Artificial Intelligence (AI) literacy in early childhood education: an intervention <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2023.2217864>
- 5) Kariman Ramzy El Helow And Abdel-Badeeh M. Salem. The Effective Role of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Early Childhood Education Process
- 6) Lijia Chen, Pingping Chen, Zhijian Lin (2020), Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Review. IEEE Xplore Full-Text PDF
- 7) Piaget, J. (1970). *Science of education and the psychology of the child*. New York: Orion Press.
- 8) Training materials (2024). Application of artificial intelligence (AI) in early childhood education scientific research. Hanoi University of Education.
- 9) UNESCO (2021). *AI and education: Guidance for policy-makers*. Paris: UNESCO.

The Current Status of Artificial Intelligence Application in Early Childhood Education in Vietnam

<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000376709>

- 10) Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.